

**THE METHOD OF EVALUATING THE EFFICIENCY OF
BUSINESS PROCESS MANAGEMENT IN TEXTILE ENTERPRISES
DEVELOPMENT**

Djumaniyazova Mo'tabarkhan Ravshanbekovna

Doctoral student of the Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry

***Annotation.** The article examines the issue of improving the method of assessing the effectiveness of business process management in textile enterprises.*

***Key words.** Process, business process, management, efficiency, method, evaluation.*

INTRODUCTION

Due to the further increase in the demand of consumers of global textile products, the competition between the participants is becoming more and more intense. It is impossible to ensure the economic and financial stability of industrial enterprises without reconstruction of their production, without equipping them with modern advanced technology, without renewing the types of manufactured products. Also, the improvement of business process management mechanisms in the organization of modern production aimed at the rational use of all available resources should be the most important condition and source of the measures implemented for the development of the textile industry of our country and the production of exportable quality products. Therefore, the issue of objective assessment of the effectiveness of business process management of the main production of textile enterprises is of urgent importance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Currently, there are many definitions of the concept of «business process». All of them describe the business process from different perspectives. In general, all currently available definitions can be divided into two groups. The first group

of researchers (Davenport, Hammer, Oichman, Popov, Harrington) consider the concept of «business process» as an independent unit [1], the second (Porter, Sheer, Zhigunova, Loginov, methodology of the ISO 9001:2000 standard) - the concept of «process» through and further clarifying it directly in the «business process». Some authors equate the concepts of «business process» and «project» [2].

M. Hammer, the founder of the reengineering process, said: «a business process is a set of processes that create a result that is valuable for the consumer (development of a new product)» [3].

According to another researcher, T. Davenport, «a process is defined as a set of certain ordered activities and actions that exist in time and space, the beginning and end of their implementation, input and output resources are determined» [4].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY. The methodology of scientific research is the dialectic method, and statistical, selective observation, comparison, and expert evaluation methods were used in the research process.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A review of the economic literature on the issue of business process efficiency indicators showed that there is no uniform approach to the composition of indicators.

In recent years, it has become clear that it is appropriate to use a process approach in enterprises and, as we mentioned above, to consider management from the point of view of the process. In our opinion, the principle of complexity is not present in the existing approaches to the evaluation of enterprise management, they allow to obtain information about its individual aspects, not about the whole process.

In our opinion, the system for evaluating the effectiveness of the management process should include objective and subjective indicators (data obtained as a result of surveys of management personnel), which are determined by

the specific characteristics of management work (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Approach to the formation of a system of indicators describing the efficiency of business processes of industrial enterprises¹

In our opinion, the parameters of business process evaluation, such as value, quality, speed and content, are of the greatest importance for increasing the efficiency of the enterprise.

Based on the analysis of existing business process evaluation systems, we have developed a system of indicators designed to evaluate the efficiency of business processes of the enterprise.

¹Author development.

A weight coefficient was set for each indicator according to each efficiency criterion (in determining the integrated indicator for the efficiency of the enterprise, organization of management work, etc.). The weight coefficient was determined based on a survey of the importance of the indicator in the group of management experts (PC, PQ, PV, PS, etc.). It is worth noting that based on the calculation of the concordance coefficient with a value of 0,74, it was concluded that the experts' opinions are consistent with each other. This, in turn, made it possible to determine the complex indicator in the group (PC, PQ, PV, PS, etc.) using formula 1, and then the integral indicator for each efficiency criterion using formula 2 [5]. Also, integral indicators are calculated based on actual ($K_{i(h)}$) and calculated and recommended values ($K_{i(r)}$):

$$R_g. = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{K_i}{K_{max}} \right)^{L_i} \quad (1)$$

here, $R_g.$ – general indicator of groups;

K_i – the actual value of the indicator;

K_{max} – the maximum possible value of the indicator under the conditions of enterprise activity;

L_i – the weight coefficient of the indicator in the group (PC, PQ, PV, PS, etc.).

As a result of the improvement of business processes, the integral indicator of the efficiency of groups according to the criteria is calculated using the following formula:

$$R_{um.} = \sqrt[n]{\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{K_i}{K_{i(r)}} \right)^{L_i}} \quad (2)$$

here, $R_{um.}$ – integral indicator according to efficiency criterion;

n – number of process parameters ($n=4$);

L_i – the weighted coefficient of the complex indicator by parameters

(L1= L2= L3= L4).

As a result of the calculations, we obtained the following values of integral indicators for «BETLIS TEKSTIL» LLC:

- according to the criterion «performance of the enterprise (such as the performance of the controlled process)»:

$$K_{i(h)} = 0,927; K_{i(r)} = 0,960.$$

- according to the criterion of «organization of management work»:

$$K_{i(h)} = 0,812; K_{i(r)} = 0,923.$$

- according to the criterion «use of management resources»:

$$K_{i(h)} = 0,780; K_{i(r)} = 0,891.$$

- according to the criterion of «management process development»:

$$K_{i(h)} = 0,825; K_{i(r)} = 0,952.$$

In connection with the current trend of accelerating business processes, we have developed a progressive scale for evaluating integral indicators at the enterprise:

0-0.30 - «low» level;

0.31-0.50 – «medium» level;

0.51-0.70 - «good» level;

0.71-0.85 – «high» level;

0.86 and higher is a «very high» level.

According to this scale, the efficiency of business process management at «BETLIS TEKSTIL» LLC was at a «very high level».

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

We offer the following suggestions to improve the efficiency of business process management in sewing and knitting enterprises:

- development of a method for assessing the effectiveness of business process management in sewing and knitting enterprises and its successful implementation;

- grouping and describing the main business processes in the production of goods in sewing and knitting enterprises;
- development of an effective monitoring system of business process management efficiency in sewing and knitting enterprises;
- improvement of the diagnostic organizational mechanism for continuous development of business processes of textile enterprises;
- formation of a new form of management structural structure from a task approach to a process approach, which reflects the content, characteristics and mechanism of the manager's influence on the managed system in textile enterprises, and the development of appropriate management mechanisms;
- improvement of process management technology by developing a computerized system of diagnostics and forecasting of business processes in textile enterprises.

REFERENCES

1. Andersen B. (2013). Business process. Instrumenty sovershenstvovaniya / B. Andersen; per. English S. V. Arinicheva nauch. ed. Yu.P. Adler. - 165 p. - Moscow: Standarty i kachestvo. - 271 p.
2. Kalyanov G.N. (2019). Theory and practice reorganization business process / G. N. Kalyanov. - Moscow: SYNTEG. - 203 p.
3. Hammer M. (2016). Reengineering corporation: manifest revolution in business / M. Hammer D. Champi; per. English Yu. E. Kornilovic. - St. Petersburg: Mann, Ivanov and Ferber. - 332 p.
4. Davenport T.H. (2013). Process innovation: reengineering work through information technology / T. N. Davenport. - Boston; Mass : Harvard Business School Press. - 337 r.

5. Varkovetsky M.M. (2016). Kolichestvennoe izmerenie kachestva produktsii v tekstilnoy promyshlennosti / M.M. Varkovetsky. - M.: «Light Industry». - 104 p.